

**THE IMPORTANCE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN PREPARING
STUDENTS FOR THE INTERNATIONAL *IELTS* TEST**

Tuychiev Adkhamjon Tukhtaboevich

Researcher, Namangan State University

**Senior English Lecturer, Namangan Institute of Engineering and
Technology**

E-mail: adham.tuychiev@gmail.com

Abstract. In order to successfully train specialists in various fields, education programs must meet the requirements of the modern world. To have some knowledge and skills in your professional field is not enough to become a highly qualified specialist in modern socio-economic conditions. There is also a need for professionals who are able to evaluate, analyze and think critically through mastering the English language. This article will consider important approaches and applying “critical thinking” in the IELTS and other international testing systems and gaining high scores in such testing types.

Keywords: IELTS, critical thinking skills, sections, band, vocabulary, apply.

The IELTS exam, an international English language proficiency testing system, is now widely used both as a student assessment tool and as a reliable student assessment tool. Regardless of the significance of this exam and the demand in the modern academic world, it seems necessary to consider what impact the preparation for the IELTS exam and the very procedure for passing it on students’ learning and what accompanying and, possibly, unplanned processes and changes occur in the perception and consciousness of the students themselves.

There is a well-known notion that passing international exams has a significant impact on both the educational system and society as a whole [1].

Many linguists, such as Philip Vernon, Alan Davis, Bruce Pearson, have written about the power that exams have over all the processes taking place in the classroom. Thus, Pearson, for example, argues that “the generally accepted view is that exams affect the attitudes, behavior and motivation of teachers, students and their parents and, ultimately, this has an inverse effect on the learning process, as teachers and students do what they would not do in a different situation” [2]. Vernon believes that such exams destroy the curriculum, believing that teachers tend to ignore those types of work that do not contribute to the success of the exam and pay excessive attention to coaching on specific exam tasks [3]. Since more and more attention is paid in the field of teaching English to taking into account the needs of students, their individual learning style and personality, while the IELTS exam involves the acquisition of fairly unified knowledge and a very specific format in various aspects, it is interesting to analyze how it meets the needs and the needs of students in mastering the knowledge they lack.

So, you have decided to go to the USA, England, Canada, Australia, New Zealand or another country of your choice for work or study. You want to improve your English. One day you see an ad that claims to help you memorize the entire Oxford Dictionary in one month and you join the program. Can you imagine what will happen after that? Can you speak English well or write good essays? You may make a number of grammatical errors. Then you join another grammar program and learn a lot of grammar rules. Now you can use good vocabulary and form grammatically correct sentences. Does this guarantee that you can write and speak to get a high IELTS score?

Probably one component is missing here. Critical thinking. Critical thinking is the ability of a person to think rationally and clearly. This involves understanding the logical connection between ideas and the mind. A critical

thinker becomes an active learner, not just a passive receiver of information. Critical thinkers can systematically identify, analyze, and solve problems [4].

In other words, critical thinking is the central intellectual skill that higher education seeks to develop in students. This includes an attitude of “reflexive skepticism” towards information and ideas. This means thinking deeply about the ideas you come across in readings, lectures, and other learning materials and asking them questions.

Surely, critical thinking and the IELTS exam are related? This question is initially confusing. It must be firmly understood that no one can get a high score without demonstrating critical thinking skills on the IELTS exam. Vocabulary, grammar, etc. represent knowledge, but critical thinking is the application of knowledge.

For most IELTS candidates, memorizing long lists of vocabulary, working through grammar exercises, and pronunciation exercises are the only ways to improve IELTS exam scores. However, a key part of any language is your ability to think in that language. To truly know a language, you must be able to dream, plan, create, judge, argue, and more while thinking in that language [7].

Why is critical thinking really important to your assessment?

Looking at descriptions of IELTS scores, band of 7 and above require you to fully understand, resolve difficult situations, and use detailed reasoning. This means that if you want to get a higher score, you will have to demonstrate on the test that you can do these things in English.

To further explain this idea, critical thinking is about applying the knowledge and experience you have gained throughout your life. Then, in a logical way, you use knowledge and experience to understand or explain the world around you [8].

Therefore, when preparing, remember not only to memorize phrases and vocabulary lists. Train your critical thinking and do it in English. It's more

interesting, it will make you a sharper thinker, and it will give you the high IELTS score you're aiming for!

How to demonstrate critical thinking in all four sections of IELTS?

We encourage you to demonstrate your ability to think critically in all four skill areas: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Let's see what critical thinking means in each of the four sections of the IELTS exam:

Reading

There are so many examples of critical thinking in IELTS Reading. One of the best examples is a True/False/Not Set question. This activity exercises your ability to read carefully and think about the ideas in the text. By truly understanding what you are reading and then reflecting on it, you should be able to reason about whether something is right, wrong, or missing information. You may be lucky with some simple questions, but many of them will require you to think about what you read in order to get the right answer [10].

Writing

Along with the usual skills such as paragraphing, vocabulary use, and grammatical range, you will have to demonstrate well-developed, fully expanded, and well-founded ideas. This means thinking carefully about the essay question and coming up with a reasonable and logical answer. Some common strategies for doing this are mind-mapping and justification.

Listening

There are several tasks for which you need to be witty. One example of a skill you need to excel at is pairing your fluent listening with synonyms when applying it to a situation. As you may know from your training, the Listening test uses many synonyms from the IELTS test book. However, you need to listen not only to synonyms, but also to the context in which they are used.

Speaking

You will certainly also have to demonstrate your English thinking skills. In the first and second parts of the test, you may be able to survive using normal everyday conversations such as shopping, watching TV, and talking about your home. However, the third part of the speaking test is the discussion. In this part, the examiner's task is to push you towards a fluent and thoughtful answer to the topic. The examiner will ask you tough questions to make sure you can answer quickly and don't stumble and mess around with translated memorized phrases [13].

In a nutshell. While it's important to practice general language skills such as common phrases, grammar patterns, and pronunciation patterns, do not forget that critical thinking in English is a key part of getting a good IELTS score. Therefore, your personal mentor should train you so that you learn to think critically. Remember that good preparation is the key to doing well on the IELTS exam.

In the end, I want to emphasize one more point, based on my many years of experience, I can say that strict requirements,

In the end, I want to emphasize one more point, based on my many years of experience, I can say that the strict requirements, useful tips and rules mentioned above apply not only to the IELTS exam, but also to other international types of testing such as TOEFL, TESOL, APTIS, GRE, GMAT, CELTA, DELTA, etc. Otherwise, without developing critical thinking, you will not be able to achieve the intended goal in such types of exams.

References

1. Tuhtaboevich, T. A. (2023). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS FOR UNIVERSITY SUCCESS IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY. Open Access Repository, 9(3), 125-132.
2. Pearson I. (1988). Tests as levers for change / D. Chamberlain & R.J. Baumgardner (eds.). – London: Modern English Publications, – P. 98–107.

3. Vernon P.E. (1956). *The Measurement of Abilities* (2nd ed.) – London: University of London Press.
4. Тўйчиев, А. (2023). СУҚРОТ МЕТОДИ–ТАНҚИДИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИ ЎРГАТИШНИНГ САМАРАЛИ УСУЛИ СИФАТИДА. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 5(5).
5. Данилина К. В. (1981). Взаимодействие видов речевой деятельности при обучении иностранным языкам //сб. ст. — М.: Наука, — С. 41–48.
6. Леонтьев А. А. (2005). *Язык, речь, речевая деятельность*. — М.: КомКнига.
7. Tuhtabaevich, T. A. (2023). The Content and Performance Indicators of Experimental Work on the Development of Critical Thinking in Teaching English. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 369-376.
8. Tuychiev, A.T. (2021). The role and importance of critical thinking at teaching English. Article. – Journal “Herald Pedagogiki”. Warsaw, Poland.
9. Wallace C. (1992). Critical literacy awareness in the EFL classroom // *Critical language awareness*. — L, NY: Longman, — P. 59–93.
10. Tuychiev, A.T. (2019). THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN THE STUDY A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES. Republican scientific-theoretical conference, Namangan, 6-7.
11. IELTS Research. Analysis of test data. 2012: <http://ielts.org/researchers/analysis-of-test-data/test-taker-performance-2012.aspx> (date of access: 25.02.2016).
12. Nunan D. (1988). *The Learner-Centered Curriculum: A Study in Second Language Teaching*. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
13. Тўйчиев, А. Т. (2020). ISSUES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING. *Булатовские чтения*, 7, 166-167.

